

DISORDERS OF OESOPHAGEAL MOTILITY – ACHALASIA

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Abstract

Achalasia is a rare primary motor disorder of the oesophagus, characterized by the failure of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) to relax and by the absence of peristalsis, resulting in symptoms such as dysphagia, regurgitation, and weight loss. During routine dissection of the posterior mediastinum at the Anatomy Department of the Medical University of Pleven, an anatomical anomaly involving the esophagus was observed, prompting further investigation into esophageal motor disorders. This article integrates clinical, diagnostic, and therapeutic perspectives on achalasia with particular attention to anatomical context.

A classification of achalasia into types I, II, and III is discussed, along with diagnostic tools such as barium studies, high-resolution manometry, and endoscopy. Treatment options—ranging from pneumatic dilation and Heller myotomy to botulinum toxin injections—are reviewed, with emphasis on their mechanisms and limitations. Psychological effects, including anxiety, depression, and social withdrawal, are also addressed, highlighting the need for a multidisciplinary approach.

This case underscores the importance of anatomical variations in understanding the pathophysiology of achalasia. Although there is no definitive cure, tailored treatment strategies and long-term follow-up can significantly improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

Keywords: motor disorders, achalasia, esophagus, LES, dysphagia.

This article presents a case observed during demonstratorship at the Anatomy Department of Medical University of Pleven (MUP), where an anatomical anomaly was discovered in a cadaver while performing a dissection of the posterior mediastinum. Upon removal of the pericardium, unusual structural deviations were identified, warranting further examination (Fig.1). This report details the findings, implications, and possible relevance of such anomalies in clinical and surgical settings.

Figure 1 - Dissected cadaver displaying the oesophagus with characteristic features of achalasia, including dilation. - Anatomy Department - MUP

Anatomy

The oesophagus is a fibromuscular organ of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), about 25 cm long, through which foods and liquids pass by peristalsis^[1] (rhythmic contractions of the muscles which propagate down the esophagus). It extends from the pharynx to the stomach and for this reason three portions can be identified: cervical, thoracic and abdominal (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – accessed 22 September 2024, "KnowledgeWorks - Drawing Oesophagus: upper and loweresophageal sphincters - English labels" by KnowledgeWorks Global Ltd, is licensed under CC BY 4.0. Photo edited by John Polos

It is provided by two sphincters that act to prevent the entry of air and the reflux of gastric contents, respectively: upper and lower esophageal sphincter^{[1][2]} (UES and LES) (Fig.2; Fig.3).

Figure 3 – Source: D. J. Sugarbaker, R. Bueno, Y. L. Colson, M. T. Jaklitsch, M. J. Krasna, S. J. Mentzer, M. Williams, A. Adams: *Adult Chest Surgery, 2nd Edition*: www.accesssurgery.com Copyright © McGraw-Hill Education. All rights reserved. , accessed 22 September 2024, <https://i0.wp.com/thoracickey.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/m_p9780071781893-ch037_f001.png?w=960>

Introduction to motor disorders

Motor disorders of the esophagus include *hypomotility* (achalasia) as well as *hypermotility* (DES, Diffuse Esophageal Spasm)^{[3][4]}.

These disorders can involve the superior portion, pharyngo-oesophageal, of the organ, equipped with striated muscles, or they can involve the inferior portion, cardio-oesophageal, affecting the smooth musculature (Fig.4).

Disorders in the pharyngo-esophageal portion are, for example:

- achalasia of the proximal sphincter
- pharyngeal paralysis
- globus hystericus (throat fullness)

Disorders in the cardio-esophageal portion are, for example (Fig.4):

- classic esophageal achalasia (lower esophageal achalasia)
- correlated dyschalasia (or Dyskinesia, mainly DES)^[3]

Figure 4 - Manometric classification of different esophageal motility disorders based on CC v4.0. HRIM= High Resolution Impedance Manometry. IRP=Integrated Relaxation Pressure, EGJOO=Esophagogastric Junction Outflow Obstruction, TBE= Tightness of the Basal Esophageal, IME= Integrated Manometric Evaluation. Accessed 22 September 2024; Patel, Dhyanes A., Rena Yadlapati, and Michael F. Vaezi. "Esophageal Motility Disorders: Current Approach to Diagnostics and Therapeutics." *Gastroenterology*, vol. 162, no. 6, 2022, pp. 1617-1634. Elsevier, doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2021.12.289.

Definition of Achalasia

Achalasia (also called cardiospasm, esophageal aperistalsis, megaesophagus) is a rare motor disorder characterized by the failure of relaxation in conjunction with the peristaltic waves of the smooth muscles in the GIT sphincters (Fig.5).

Figure 5 - Difference between Normal LES and Oesophageal Achalasia

Accessed 22 September 2024, GBMC, Gastrointestinal, Bariatric & Metabolic Center, Achalasia, <[tps://www.gbmc-jo.com/en/achalasia/](https://www.gbmc-jo.com/en/achalasia/)>

This leads to dilation and elongation of the organ with mucosal lesions, secondary to the stagnation of the content. Oesophageal (or cardio-oesophageal) achalasia can be classified as^{[4][7]}:

- Classic – *Type I*

- Vigorous (initial) – *Type II (or Achalasia with compression) and Type III (spastic)*
- Decompensated – late stage

Characteristic	Type I	Type II	Type III	Decompensated
Prevalence	20%-40% (second most common)	50% (most common)	5% (least common)	Progression from earlier stages
Peristalsis	100% failed (aperistalsis)	100% failed (aperistalsis)	Spastic contractions	No peristalsis, significantly impaired
Panesophageal Pressurization*	Absent (less than 30 mmHg)	Present (greater than 30 mmHg)	May be present or absent	Typically, absent
Contractions	None	None	Abnormal contractions obliterating lumen	Weak contractions, often with dilation
Oesophageal dilation	Minimal dilation	Moderate dilation due to pressurization	Possible due to spastic activity	Severe dilation (megaesophagus)

Table 1 – Differences between Achalasia Types I, II and III, Daniela Perrone

**refers to the simultaneous increase in pressure throughout the entire oesophagus, typically seen during high-resolution oesophageal manometry.*

This dysfunction leads to a constant contraction of the LES inhibiting the normal passage of foods and liquids through it with consequent collection of material in the esophagus that will be regurgitated^[34].

Etiology

Achalasia is a rare disorder primarily caused by the dysfunction of the nerves that regulate the esophagus's rhythmic muscle contractions, particularly those controlling the lower esophageal sphincter (LES). While the exact cause remains unknown in most cases, both viral and autoimmune factors are suspected^{[5][6]}. Moreover, symptoms similar to achalasia can result from secondary factors, including tumors (which directly invade the oesophageal nerves) or infections (such as Chagas disease, which leads to the destruction of autonomic ganglion clusters). The latter form is frequent in South-America.

The incidence of achalasia in Europe and North America is approximately 1 per 100,000 people annually, with no significant variations in prevalence across ethnicities or sexes^[6]. While extremely rare in children, achalasia predominantly affects adults, with the highest incidence seen between ages 40 and 60. Secondary forms are known by:

- Carcinomatous or lymphomatous infiltration

- Chronic intestinal pseudo-obstruction (neurologic type)
- Irritation by drugs and toxins^{[8][9]}

Symptoms

Classic symptoms:

- Dysphagia
- Regurgitation
- Weight loss
- Discontinuous retrosternal pain
- Nocturnal cough crisis in some cases
- Bronchopulmonary infections (10% of cases)^{[5][10][11]}

As the disease advances, regurgitation of undigested food becomes more frequent, and aspiration may pose a life-threatening risk.

	Type I	Type II	Type III	Decompensated
Symptoms	Dysphagia, regurgitation	Dysphagia, chest pain, regurgitation	Severe chest pain, Dysphagia, regurgitation	Severe dysphagia, weight loss, risk of aspiration

Table 2 – Differentiation of types of Achalasia symptoms, Daniela Perrone

Diagnosis

Diagnosis can be made with a standard *chest X-ray*, which typically shows the characteristic double mediastinal stripe along the entire length of the chest and a retrocardiac air-fluid level in a patient presenting with typical symptoms^[12] (Fig. 6 A-C).

Radiologic *contrastography in Trendelenburg* demonstrates minimal achalasia only at fluoroscopic observation due to the absence of peristalsis and non-coordinated contraction in the distal esophagus^{[22][23][24][25][26]}. The cardiac opening at the deglutition is complete. When walls atonia are revealed with moderate dilation, lengthening and stagnation, we can talk about mild achalasia. In the moderate form, the depletion of the cardiac portion is observable. The severe form is diagnosed when the dilation reaches 10 cm (megaesophagus) with S-shape of the esophagus.

The following images show the typical placement of the patient that drinks solution (150-250mL Barium-Sulfate low-density (45% W/V)) in a maximum of 20 seconds.

Figure 6 - Left posterior oblique images were acquired at 1, 2, and 5 minutes post-barium ingestion.

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10 and Figure 11

These images show a dilated esophagus with evidence of stenosis in the distal third and a 'bird's beak' narrowing^{[13][14]}. After oral administration of contrast medium, a slow and reduced passage into the gastric cavity is observed.

The *manometric criteria* include the failure of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) to relax reflexively during swallowing and the absence of progressive peristalsis along the entire length of the oesophagus^{[5][15]}.

Figure 12 – NHS, Hull University Teaching Hospitals, accessed 25 September 2024, <<https://www.hey.nhs.uk/wp/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/HEY291-2019.png>>

Esophagoscopy is recommended to assess the severity of esophagitis and exclude the possibility of associated carcinoma, a distal esophageal stricture due to reflux esophagitis, or a tumor of the cardia that may mimic achalasia (pseudoachalasia)^{[16][33]}.

Complications

- Bronchiectasis
- Pulmonary fibrosis (in more than 10% of cases due to nocturnal aspiration of regurgitation)
- Phlogosis (inflammation) by stagnation
- Iatrogenic fistulation
- Squamous epithelial carcinomas (4% of cases)^{[6][17][18]}

Psychological Effects

Achalasia not only physically affects patients but also has a significant psychological impact. Patients often experience frustration and anxiety due to daily difficulties with swallowing, which can lead to social isolation^{[31][32]}. Constant worry about complications, such as malnutrition and aspiration, also contributes to feelings of depression. Patients with achalasia have a significantly reduced quality of life, with common psychological symptoms including anxiety and depression. In some cases, psychotherapy and psychological support are recommended to help patients manage the emotional aspects of the disease^[32].

Treatment

The treatment cannot restore peristalsis and sphincter relaxation, but it can be useful to ensure the draining of the esophagus^{[5][6]}.

Balloon dilation entails mechanically expanding the sphincter by inflating a large balloon within it. While this procedure is typically effective, multiple dilations may be required. There is a slight risk of esophageal rupture during the dilation, which can cause severe inflammation in the chest (mediastinitis) and, in rare instances, can be fatal if not promptly treated^{[5][19][29]}.

Definitive treatment involves disrupting the circular smooth muscle layer within the LES area. Two widely used and extensively studied therapeutic methods are forceful dilation, either pneumatic or hydrostatic, and Heller *oesophagomyotomy*^{[5][20][29][35]} (a type of minimally invasive procedure: small incisions of 2 to 3 inches long/general anesthesia).

Figure 13 - Treatment methods of achalasia: pneumatic dilatation and Heller myotomy, accessed on 29 September 2024,

Surgical Treatment

- **HELLERS MYOTOMY**
- Cutting muscle of Lower esophagus & cardia.
- Complication- GERD
- Therefore Partial Anterior Fundoplication (HELLER-DOR's operation) is added.

Heller myotomy

<<https://epos.mysr.org/posterimage/esr/ecr2018/142429/media/738024>>

Botulinum toxin injection into the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) is a pharmacologic intervention for achalasia that provides short-term relief (6 to 9 months) by temporarily paralyzing the sphincter muscle. Administered endoscopically via a flexible esophagoscope, botulinum toxin targets the neurogenic mechanism underlying LES dysfunction in achalasia blocking acetylcholine release from excitatory neurons acting on the lower esophageal sphincter. This results in a decrease in lower esophageal sphincter tone that can allow improved esophageal emptying^{[21][27][28][29][36]}.

Figure 14 – The Botox injection method (A) involves using a needle to administer injections at the squamocolumnar junction (B, C), or up to 1 cm proximally. A total of 100 IU is injected in four to five equal-volume aliquots (D), ensuring the injections are evenly spaced in a circumferential manner at the same level.

Elsevier Science, accessed on 29 September, <<https://ars.els-cdn.com/content/image/1-s2.0-S221317951400008X-gr2.jpg>>

The addition of an antireflux procedure to surgical oesophagotomy is controversial. Esophagectomy should be strongly considered for symptomatic patients with end-stage achalasia.

Certain medications, including nitrates and calcium channel blockers, have been explored but have not demonstrated significant effectiveness.

Treatment Method	Description	Pros	Cons
Pneumatic/Hydrostatic Dilatation *	Forceful dilation of the LES using pneumatic or hydrostatic methods.	Can effectively disrupt muscle layer and allow better esophageal drainage.	Risk of damage to surrounding tissues.
Heller Esophagomyotomy	Minimally invasive surgery with small incisions to cut the LES muscle.	Effective long-term solution for patients not responding to dilation.	Requires general anesthesia. Surgical risks involved.
Botulinum Toxin Injection	Injected directly into the LES to temporarily paralyze it, reducing muscle tone. Blocks acetylcholine release.	Short-term relief (6 to 9 months).	Relief is temporary, requiring repeated injections.
Esophagectomy	Complete removal of the oesophagus for the end-stage achalasia.	Should be considered for severe, symptomatic option.	Major surgery with significant risks.
Medications (Nitrates, Calcium Channels Blockers)	Medications studied for their potential to reduce LES pressure.	Potentially useful as a non-invasive option.	Limited effectiveness; not proven to significantly benefit achalasia patients.

Table 2 – Overview of Treatment Options for Achalasia, Daniela Perrone ^{[5][6][19]}

*pneumatic and hydrostatic dilatation are both types of balloon dilatation, but they differ in the medium used to inflate the balloon.

Prognosis

The prognosis for patients with achalasia largely depends on the type and stage of the disease at the time of diagnosis, as well as the chosen treatment. While therapeutic options such as pneumatic dilatation, Heller myotomy, and botulinum toxin injections can significantly improve swallowing and alleviate the difficulty in passing food, it is important to emphasize that there is no definitive cure for achalasia. The disease remains a chronic condition^[30], and in many cases, symptoms may recur over time, requiring repeated treatments.

Achalasia is particularly bothersome for patients, not only due to physical symptoms like dysphagia, regurgitation, and retrosternal pain but also because of the psychological impact it can have on quality of life. The chronic difficulty in swallowing food and liquids can cause frustration, anxiety, and a

general reduction in quality of life, while long-term complications such as aspiration and pulmonary infections can worsen the situation^{[5][6][19]}.

Despite surgical treatments, such as Heller myotomy, which involves cutting the circular muscle of the LES to allow for better swallowing, patients do not always achieve complete relief from symptoms. Some may continue to experience difficulty swallowing or regurgitation, and disease progression to more advanced stages, such as megaesophagus, may require more invasive interventions like oesophagectomy^{[19][20][30]}. Therefore, the management of the disease focuses more on reducing symptoms and preventing complications rather than offering a definitive cure^{[31][32]}.

Regular follow-up and continuous monitoring are essential for addressing any recurrence of symptoms and managing complications that may arise over time, ensuring a more personalized and attentive approach to the patient's quality of life.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Achalasia represents a rare but serious motor disorder of the esophagus, characterized by the failure of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) to relax properly, leading to significant dysphagia and other debilitating symptoms. Its classification into various types—ranging from classic achalasia to decompensated stages—allows for targeted diagnostic and therapeutic approaches, though etiology often remains elusive. While treatment cannot restore normal esophageal function, interventions like pneumatic dilatation, Heller myotomy, and botulinum toxin injections provide relief by addressing LES dysfunction and improving esophageal drainage^{[5][19][20]}. Despite surgical interventions like pneumatic dilation and Heller myotomy, complete symptom relief is not always achieved. Chronic symptoms, along with psychological distress such as anxiety and frustration, require long-term management and tailored care to improve patient outcomes and quality of life^{[5][19][31][32]}. Advanced cases may require esophagectomy to prevent life-threatening complications. Therefore, ongoing research is crucial to refine treatment strategies and ensure comprehensive care for achalasia patients^{[4][5][6][19][31]}.

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